

Small Business Boom in Ecommerce: an in-depth Research Exploration

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords: Small Business, Innovation, Technology, Social Media.

Received : 29, November

Revised : 18, December

Accepted: 22, January

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the transformative impact of e-commerce on small businesses, particularly in the context of their adoption of electronic marketing tools. Focusing on the rise of small businesses in the booming e-commerce landscape, the study delves into the challenges and opportunities faced by these enterprises, especially during and post-COVID. The investigation underscores the essential role of digital platforms, such as social media, in reshaping the global business environment. Emphasizing the importance of building trust and delivering value through customer-friendly websites, the paper also addresses key issues like cybersecurity, customer experience, and distinct value propositions. Through a mixed-methods approach, including surveys and literature reviews, the study provides insights into the strategies adopted by small businesses in embracing e-commerce, revealing a significant shift towards digitization. The findings highlight the multifaceted benefits of e-commerce, positioning it as a vital catalyst for the success and sustainability of small businesses in the evolving digital landscape.

INTRODUCTION

The transformation in news production, dissemination, and discourse is underway, driven by the increasing prevalence of social media platforms such as Facebook and Twitter. Yet, our comprehension is rudimentary regarding (1) the relative significance of social media as a news source vis-à-vis other media, (2) the extent of their utilization for news discovery, (3) the engagement levels in more interactive forms of news consumption, and (4) whether these patterns persist uniformly across nations with comparable technological advancement. In the realm of commerce, the author contends that small businesses adopting E-Marketing strategies wield the potential to reshape the global landscape and character of their operations. The surge in Internet usage and the utilization of electronic marketing tools for transactions, encompassing e-mail, intranets, extranets, and mobile phones, presents a realm of opportunities for small enterprises while mitigating associated risks. This perspective underscores the pivotal role that electronic marketing tools, inclusive of the Internet and other electronic media, play in executing marketing initiatives across diverse corporate entities, irrespective of their scale or nature.

PROFILE OF SAMPLE UNIT

Enhancing the customer-friendliness of your website is a continuous endeavor that warrants consistent attention. It is said, "Web site makes it possible for the company to grow by recruiting new customers and by securing the loyalty of existing customers" (Bellaaj, Bernard, Pecquet, & Plaisen, 2008). It's imperative to recognize that a substantial 70% of purchasing decisions are made by consumers before they engage with a sales representative or initiate a product purchase. This highlights the crucial reality that, although you might not directly influence the majority of the purchasing process, there are strategic ways to guide the initial 70% of the conversation.

Of paramount importance in this process is the establishment of trust. Trust emerges as the linchpin influencing individuals' decisions to choose a particular business. Therefore, it becomes imperative to focus on building a website that not only caters to customer needs but also fosters an environment conducive to trust, ensuring that your online platform becomes a vital part of the customer's decision-making journey.

Prioritize Value Delivery: Ensure that every page and every piece of content on your website serves a purpose by delivering genuine value to your audience. Steer clear of unnecessary filler and focus on providing meaningful insights and education. Establishing trust begins with offering tangible value in exchange for your visitors' time and attention.

Address Real Inquiries: Engage with your audience by responding to their authentic questions. Don't shy away from discussing topics that many organizations may find uncomfortable, such as pricing or competitors. Approach this from a customer's perspective, anticipating and honestly addressing every query that might arise during the sales process. Remember, trust is built on transparency, and honesty is paramount.

Embrace the Power of Video: Recognize that people connect with individuals, not just businesses. Leverage the effectiveness of video to build

trust and humanize your brand. In today's digital landscape, incorporating video into your website is essential for achieving measurable, long-term benefits. Ensure that your website includes seven crucial types of videos: 80% videos, staff bio videos, product or service videos, landing page videos, customer journey videos, videos outlining your company's promises, and a video candidly describing situations where your offerings might not be the best fit. Honest communication through video is a powerful tool for establishing authenticity and building lasting connections with your audience.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Rise of Small Business in E-commerce: Navigating Challenges and Embracing Opportunities During and Post-COVID

In the realm of commerce, small businesses, often characterized by private ownership and operation, are experiencing a significant surge in their presence within the vast landscape of e-commerce. This transformation is instrumental in enabling smaller enterprises to not only compete but thrive alongside their larger counterparts.

E-commerce's Impact on Small Businesses: A Boost Amidst Challenges

The benefits of e-commerce for small businesses are pronounced, with online purchasing emerging as a lifeline for many during challenging times. Research from eMarketer highlights that internet shopping contributed to a 3.5 percent increase in overall retail sales in 2020, amounting to an impressive \$5.6 trillion. Notably, e-commerce alone experienced a remarkable growth rate of 33.6 percent in the same year. As a research says,

Online purchasing has enabled hundreds of thousands of small businesses to not only survive, but also to prosper. According to the research company eMarketer, internet shopping increased overall retail sales by approximately 3.5 percent in 2020, to \$5.6 trillion. In 2020, e-commerce alone will have grown by 33.6 percent (Prasad & Kumar, 2023).

Adaptation Amidst Crisis: Small Businesses and the COVID Challenge

Amid the unprecedented challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic, small business owners exhibited remarkable resilience. Faced with the sudden upheaval of established business norms, these entrepreneurs displayed tenacity and adaptability. As state-wide lockdowns ensued, and subsequent partial reopenings transpired, small businesses underwent rapid transformations. Many redirected their focus towards establishing a robust e-commerce presence and expanding their digital platforms.

E-commerce as a Survival Strategy: Statistics and Insights

Statistics from Alibaba.com underscore the pivotal role of e-commerce in the survival playbook of small enterprises. A report reveals that 93% of businesses now conduct some portion of their operations online, showcasing a notable increase from 90% in December 2019. Additionally, 43% of these businesses actively utilize e-commerce, marking an 8% surge within the same time frame.

In essence, the rise of small businesses in e-commerce is not merely a response to challenges but a strategic shift that positions them to thrive in the dynamic and evolving landscape of digital commerce. The adaptability

demonstrated during the COVID era has forged a path where e-commerce is not just a survival strategy but a defining element of the future for small businesses.

Led to digitization

The Internet has experienced exponential growth, doubling in size annually in recent years and creating a global network for the seamless exchange of digital data. The most recent advancements have been marked by a surge in new commercial activities. Despite extensive coverage in mainstream media, there is a limited understanding of the influence the Internet is exerting on businesses utilizing this platform for conducting commerce. As research says,

The Internet has doubled in size every year in recent years and now spans the globe, facilitating the exchange of all matter of digital data. Recent development has been categorized by an explosion in new commercial activity. Despite overwhelming coverage in the popular press, relatively little is understood regarding the impact the Internet is having on firms that use this medium to facilitate commerce (Auger & Gallagher, 1997).

Small businesses have swiftly embraced digitization, utilizing e-commerce as a pivotal platform for this transformative shift. The initiation of online sales by small enterprises has not only granted them access to an expansive customer base but has also presented lucrative opportunities for growth and expansion. This proactive move towards digital channels has catalyzed an inherent synergy between small business operations and the latest technological advancements.

Examining the impact of a small business in the context of Bangladesh sheds light on the significant contributions of these enterprises to the national economy. From traditional handicrafts to local grocery stores, pharmacies, hardware shops, mobile retailers, recharge businesses, and local fruit and vegetable vendors, small businesses form the backbone of various industries. These diverse sectors collectively play a crucial role in job creation, providing sustenance for a considerable portion of the Bangladeshi population.

In essence, the dynamic partnership between small business endeavors and the digital landscape, epitomized by e-commerce, underscores a transformative narrative. This narrative not only enriches the economic fabric but also exemplifies the adaptability and resilience ingrained in the entrepreneurial spirit, ensuring the continued prosperity of small businesses within the evolving digital landscape.

Because of the pandemic last year, most businesses suffered greatly and faced significant losses; nevertheless, internet shopping had a positive response and the business expanded significantly. Because people were unable to go out in crowded areas and do their own shopping, they opted for sitting at their homes and ordering products, such as clothing, groceries, medicines, or vegetables, as well as power (Kumia, 2006)

However, each of these advantages and disadvantages will be analysed in greater depth in connection to these fundamental principles. As a result, the goal of this review of literature is to emphasise what has been done and what

future researchers and educators may learn from a wide range of findings in the classroom context.

Given its recent emergence, the term "social media" can be classified within more comprehensive and established frameworks (Chen, 2003). Among these, Information and Communications Technology (ICT) stands out as one of the most recognized and extensively studied categories. ICT encompasses a wide spectrum of interactive and non-interactive mediums, ranging from interactive whiteboards to offline computer games. In instances like offline computer games, the audience is confined to individuals physically present and engaged with the medium at the time.

METHODOLOGY

This study aims to investigate the multifaceted aspects of e-commerce platforms, focusing on the operational procedures involved in product showcasing, customer transactions, and the subsequent fulfillment processes. Employing a mixed-methods research approach, this methodology integrates both quantitative and qualitative methodologies to provide a comprehensive understanding of the intricate dynamics within the e-commerce landscape.

Primary data collection: A questionnaire has been devised to collect primary data from small business employers in order to investigate the impact of e-commerce on small businesses in Dhaka, Bangladesh. We emailed Google forms to a few small business owners to measure the level of e-commerce adoption in their firm.

Secondary data gathering: We collected secondary data from a variety of journals, books, periodicals, and websites containing technical information.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

E-commerce enterprises encounter challenges across various dimensions, necessitating strategic responses to mitigate these issues. Victor Congioni, Chief Information Officer and Co-founder of Proven Data, emphasizes the critical importance of establishing robust cybersecurity policies and technologies, particularly for small e-commerce ventures. He underscores the need for comprehensive rules and procedures to fortify the cybersecurity framework, highlighting that disruptions caused by cyberattacks can be financially perilous for small businesses, heavily reliant on each transaction's success.

Conjoint asserts that small business owners aspire to implement effective cybersecurity measures to safeguard data while empowering employees to adeptly deploy procedures and technologies against potential assaults. The economic viability of small firms is intricately tied to the efficacy of their cybersecurity framework.

For businesses primarily engaged in e-commerce or those venturing into online selling, providing customers with a comparable experience to brick-and-mortar stores poses a challenge. George Dunham, CEO of epaCUBE, identifies pricing and client segmentation as often overlooked aspects of the consumer experience during the transition to e-commerce. Dunham emphasizes that, when embarking on an e-commerce initiative, ensuring a seamless customer

experience is crucial as customers anticipate online treatment equivalent to in-person interactions. In the competitive e-commerce landscape, small businesses grapple with various rivals, requiring them to match aggressive pricing, offer competitive goods, and deliver superior services to capture their target audience. Actually e-commerce “empowers us (business) to engage confidently with international business partners, fostering connections with people worldwide.” (Barat & Jobaar, 2023)

Calloway Cook, Founder of Illuminate Labs, suggests that developing a distinct company value proposition that clients cannot find elsewhere is pivotal for small firms to withstand pricing competition. In the saturated e-commerce industry, distinguishing oneself becomes challenging, making it imperative for businesses to articulate a unique value proposition to stand out amid the competition.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- Minimal Operational Costs
- To Increase Revenue And Profitability
- To Grow With The Market Trend And Attain Changes.
- E-Commerce May Be Flawlessly Incorporated Into The Strategies Of Small Businesses.
- Every Percentage Of Customer Advocacy
- Increasing Sales In Ecommerce Stores.
- Increasing Brand Awareness.
- Attracting More Visitors.
- Increasing Client Satisfaction.
- A Minimum Of Shopping Cart Returns.
- Riskier Conversion Rates.
- Getting Into Continuing Business.
- Enhancing The User's' Encounter

SCOPE OF STUDY

Merchants establish online platforms showcasing product images, accompanied by detailed descriptions and pricing information. Customers availing themselves of these products enjoy a variety of payment options, including Cash on Delivery (COD), e-wallets, net banking, credit cards, among others. The responsibility of the online seller encompasses not only processing the transaction but also ensuring the secure and punctual dispatch of the purchased merchandise to the buyer.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Do you have an e-commerce system in your organization?

Yes	No
83	17

2. How long have you been using e-commerce in your organisation?

Last one year	10
Last three years	50
Last five years	25
More than five years	15

3. Do you believe that e-commerce has an edge over traditional commercial transactions?

Yes	92
No	8

4. What factors prompted you to implement e-commerce technologies in your organisation?

Upgrade Business Operations	To deal with suppliers	Data maintenance	Time Efficiency
45	5	35	15

5. Which of these e-technologies are you implementing in your company?

Internet	Credit Card	E-shopping	E-wallet	Bio metric	Fax
65	17	13	3	1	1

6. Which factors did you examine while deciding on an e-commerce system for your company?

Personal Recommendation	Brand Name	Cost Factors	Technical Support offered
58	22	9	11

7. Did you encounter any of the following issues when you first installed and began utilising the e-commerce?

Deciding on Equipment Selection	0
Lack of information	
Difficulty in using equipment	
No problems experienced	3

8. To what extent have you encountered any of the following issues with the Internet or e-commerce since you first began using it?

Security breach	Maintenance most costly than expected	Reliability Service	No problem experinced
7	7	16	70

9. In what ways has the usage of e-commerce benefited your business?

Increased Sales	0
Improving customer Relationship	0
Improving Supplier Relationship	

	0
Speed up Process like transactions, recruitment, marketing, etc.	0
Keeping upto date with external business environment	
Internal Communication	
Convenience	0

10. Do you provide employee training when adopting e-commerce technology?

Yes	No
10	90

LIMITATIONS

- In general, the accuracy of the respondents' responses determines the findings of surveys.
- Although there are millions of users of online marketplaces, our research relies on a select group of small business owners.

FINDINGS

- Table 1 shows that 83 percent of small business owners have ecommerce facilities in their organisation.
- Table 2 shows the usage of E commerce in the organisation for 5 exceeding years.
- Table 3 shows the pie of the respondents sharing their views on e-commerce having a benefit over traditional methods.
- Table 4 shows the ideology of the employee's motivation in picking e commerce in their organisation.
- Table 5 shows the adaptation being chosen to finish complied tasks assigned.
- Table 6 shows the factors the respondents consider while selecting e-commerce.
- Table 7 depicts if the organisation faced any problems while adapting to e-commerce.
- Table 8 shows what problems were faced by them while pre developing of e-commerce as a whole.
- In Table 9 the survey asks the respondents to pick what has been the most benefits to their businesses.
- Table 10 asks the organisations if they help out employees in the change of the platform.

SUGGESTIONS

- Selling goods that assist customers in achieving their personal or professional objectives through an educational platform is a fantastic method to generate passive income.

- It has become fairly popular to sell items that have been thrifted, purchasing products that have been thrifted and then flipped has become popular.
- Local sourcing is a growing trend that is advantageous to your company and neighbourhood stakeholders.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In a digital era where more than 70% of internet users actively engage in social networks, dedicating an average of at least one hour each day, it is evident that social platforms have evolved into a virtual reality fostering communication, engagement, and trust. Notably, over 60% of these users access social media via mobile devices, with strong indications suggesting a continual upward trajectory in the coming years.

In this societal landscape, it is imperative to acknowledge that social networks have transcended personal interactions and seamlessly integrated into the commercial sector, constituting a new dimension of reality. A resounding 90% of marketers either currently leverage or plan to utilize social media for business purposes, with more than 60% intending to do so in the immediate future.

As evidenced by the findings of the present survey, e-commerce emerges as a multifaceted solution for small business owners, providing diverse avenues for growth. It facilitates seamless interaction with both consumers and suppliers, expedites processes, and extends critical support to small businesses. The study extensively explores the pivotal role of e-commerce in fostering the expansion of small businesses. Notably, the overwhelming majority of small businesses in Bangalore actively embrace e-commerce services, including internet platforms, credit cards, and e-wallets, underscoring the instrumental role of digital commerce in the operational landscape of small enterprises. This widespread adoption reflects the transformative impact of e-commerce, affirming its position as a crucial catalyst for the success and sustainability of small businesses in the contemporary business environment.

ADVANCED RESEARCH

Each study has limitations; thus, you can describe it here and briefly provide suggestions for further research.

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